

Eradicating Hepatitis C in Europe

A frontline
assessment of harm
reduction and
implementation gaps

Civil Society Monitoring of
Harm Reduction in Europe **2025**

Correlation

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Map 1: Location of C-EHRN Focal Points and years of contribution to the monitoring study, 2020–2025.

This report is based on data collected in 2025 from C-EHRN Focal Points: civil society organizations delivering harm reduction services in 42 European cities.

42 Cities surveyed across Europe
33 Countries represented
83% of Focal Points are frontline harm reduction providers

Methodology

Since 2018, Correlation — European Harm Reduction Network (C-EHRN) has gathered data from civil society organizations across Europe active in harm reduction. In 2018, a pilot of the monitoring was launched. In 2019, the monitoring was done at a national level, and in 2020, we switched it to the city level, reflecting the information the focal points were providing.

The 2025 data collection used a revised questionnaire designed to improve indicator measurement.

1

Highlights

The Cure Exists. The Barriers Are Political

Hepatitis C is curable. Direct-acting antiviral medicines achieve cure rates above 95% [1]. Nearly every death from Hepatitis C in Europe today is preventable, and yet people who inject drugs continue to be denied testing, treatment, and follow-up care, not because of a lack of medicine, but because of discrimination, broken healthcare pathways, and chronic underfunding.

The WHO 2030 Target Is at Risk

The World Health Organization [2] targets for hepatitis C elimination aim to end HCV as a public health threat by reducing new infections by 90% and deaths by 65%, while ensuring that 90% of people are diagnosed and 80% of those eligible receive treatment.

Achieving these targets requires a combination of key strategies, including the widespread use of highly effective direct-acting antivirals (DAAs), targeted screening of high-risk populations such as people who inject drugs, the expansion of harm reduction services (e.g. needle and syringe programs and opioid agonist therapy), and progress towards universal access to treatment.

With just 5 years remaining, frontline civil society data shows that European cities still face critical gaps in testing access, treatment equity, post-cure follow-up, and most concerning, in tackling the discrimination that prevents people who use drugs from using services even when they exist.

Key Figures

93% of cities (39 of 42) have HCV testing available, but access is deeply unequal.

36% of cities (15 of 42) impose financial barriers that exclude migrants and refugees; another 12 cities exclude the uninsured.

62% of cities (26 of 42) report that their harm reduction organizations face serious limitations in delivering HCV care; underfunding is the single most common cause, cited in 21 cities.

50% of cities (21 of 42) have systematic re-testing for people cured of HCV who remain at risk.

1. World Health Organization (WHO). Hepatitis C. 2025. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hepatitis-c>
2. World Health Organization (WHO). Global Health Sector Strategy On Viral Hepatitis 2016–2021. 2016. <https://iris.who.int/server/api/core/bitstreams/a3141927-6df2-4c43-828b-90c965012f2e/content>

2

Testing

Getting Tested: A Fractured Pathway

Testing is the first step to eliminating Hepatitis C; you cannot treat what you do not know about. Recent reports estimate that over 60% of people living with chronic HCV in the EU/EEA are undiagnosed and unaware of their infection [3]. Our frontline data reveals that while basic testing is widely available, the road from a first rapid test to confirmed diagnosis and treatment is fragmented and dependent on which door a person happens to walk through.

What We Found

Hepatitis C testing is available in 39 of the 42 cities surveyed. This is a positive baseline, but "available" does not mean being accessible. Self-tests, which people can use privately without visiting a clinic, are available in only 16 cities (38%). This matters: self-testing removes one of the biggest barriers: fear of stigma to finding out one's status.

More troubling is what happens after a positive rapid antibody test. Only 57% of cities (24 of 42) always perform a follow-up confirmatory test. This means that in the remaining 16 cities, people are left in a diagnostic limbo knowing they may have Hepatitis C but not knowing for certain and not receiving treatment.

Cities with HCV Testing

Figure 1. Did HCV testing for people who inject drugs (other than self-tests) exist in the past year in your city? (n=42).

3. European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). World Hepatitis Day 2025: Hepatitis burden remains high across the EU/EEA, with the majority of people unaware they are infected. 2025. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/news-events/world-hepatitis-day-2025>

Cities with HCV Self-Tests

Figure 2. Are self-tests for HCV (that can be used without professional assistance) available for people who inject drugs in your city? (n=42).

Cities that Always Do Confirmatory Tests

Figure 3. If someone tests positive on a screening test, is a confirmatory test routinely performed? (n=42).

What Good Looks Like

Harm reduction services are the most accessible first-contact venue for testing in 34 of 42 cities. Cities should integrate rapid Hepatitis C testing into harm reduction services, where people who inject drugs already go.

WHO Harm Reduction Targets

The WHO recommends at least 300 sterile syringes distributed per person who injects drugs per year [4] and opioid agonist therapy coverage of at least 50% of people with opioid dependence [4]. Our data is collected at city level; country-level coverage figures come from EUDA [5]. Taken together, they suggest only a handful of European countries meet both targets simultaneously [5]. Countries that fail to meet these targets are undermining Hepatitis C elimination, because without harm reduction, new infections will continue at rates that outpace treatment capacity.

Figure 4. Care providers conducting HCV testing for people who inject drugs, by test type (n = 42 cities, 2025).

- World Health Organization (WHO). Consolidated Guidelines on HIV, Viral Hepatitis and STI Prevention, Diagnosis, Treatment and Care for Key Populations. 1st ed. World Health Organization; 2022.
- European Union Drugs Agency (EUDA). Harm Reduction – the Current Situation in Europe (European Drug Report 2025). 2025. https://www.euda.europa.eu/publications/european-drug-report/2025/harm-reduction_en

The Testing Pathway Problem

The most striking pattern in our data is the sharp shift between where people get their initial rapid test and where they must go for everything that follows. Harm reduction services lead for initial rapid screening (34 cities); these are low-threshold, community-embedded spaces. But for confirmatory testing, people must generally go to Infectious Disease Clinics (32 cities) or Gastroenterology Clinics (24 cities). These are settings where discrimination against people who use drugs is frequently reported.

This is not just an inconvenience; it is a structural barrier that causes people to drop out of the care pathway before ever receiving a diagnosis. Every point of transition between services is a point where someone can be lost.

Frontline Voice [London]

"Hep C Care is actually one arena where people who use drugs experience relatively less stigma compared to most other healthcare areas - this is in large part thanks to the Hep C Trust's large network of peers delivering trainings and services to challenge poor practice. In general, stigma against People Who Use Drugs still exists - and pharmacies and GPs will continue to be sites for that, especially as both of those venues actually are not commonly sites for HCV treatment in England"

Figure 5. Venues where people who inject drugs can access HCV testing, by test type (n = 42 cities, 2025). (a) Point-of-care rapid antibody testing (oral fluid or capillary blood); (b) Confirmatory HCV RNA blood testing.

3

**Treatment
Access**

Treatment Access: Progress and Exclusion

Direct-acting antiviral medicines can cure Hepatitis C in 8–12 weeks with minimal side effects [6]. They are approved across all European countries. Yet frontline evidence shows that in too many cities, the cure is available, but not for everyone.

Most cities (74%, 31 of 42) no longer restrict direct-acting antiviral access by fibrosis stage, a clear improvement. But who actually reaches treatment depends on insurance, immigration status, and current drug use.

Direct-acting antiviral treatment exclusion rules	City
Accessible for F1, F2, F3, F4 (treatment available for people with any stage of liver fibrosis, from mild fibrosis to cirrhosis).	Podgorica
Accessible only for F2, F3, F4 (treatment available for people with moderate or advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis)	Saint Petersburg
Accessible only for F3 and F4 (treatment available for people with severe fibrosis or cirrhosis)	Kyiv, Tirana
Other restrictions based on the stage of fibrosis	Skopje, Lisbon, London
There are no restrictions based on the stage of their fibrosis	31 / 42 Cities

Liver Disease Severity Requirements for Treatment

- There are no restrictions based on the stage of their fibrosis
- There are certain restrictions based on the fibrosis stage
- I am not able / I do not want to answer this question

.Figure 6. Do restrictions on accessing DAAs exist based on the stage of fibrosis for people diagnosed with HCV? (n=42).

Figure 7. Do the following types of financial restrictions apply to accessing DAAs? (n=42).

In 20 of 42 cities, DAA treatment costs are not fully covered for at least some populations; 18 of these reported at least one specific financial restriction. The uninsured face partial or full costs in 12 cities. Migrants and refugees face financial exclusion in 15 cities. Five cities still use current drug use as grounds for denial, a practice every clinical guideline rejects.

5 cities still use current drug use as a reason to deny access to Hepatitis C treatment, despite evidence that treatment is equally effective in people who use drugs, and despite guidelines recommending that drug use should never be an exclusion criterion.

Figure 8. Which professionals are, legally, allowed to prescribe direct-acting antivirals (DAAs)? (n=42).

Only Specialist Doctors Can Prescribe in Most Cities

In 34 cities, Infectious Disease specialists are legally authorized prescribers. In 32 cities, gastroenterology and hepatology specialists can prescribe. Only 11 cities allow general practitioners to prescribe direct-acting antivirals. This means treatment remains bottlenecked in specialist settings, lengthening the path of care to obtain treatment.

 Frontline Voice · Saint Petersburg

“Medical professionals tend to frown upon people who use drugs considering them to be unstable and not treatment-adherent”

4

Care Continuum

The Care Journey: Harm Reduction Services as a Lifeline

Getting cured of Hepatitis C is not the end of the story. People who continue to inject drugs after treatment remain at high risk of re-infection. And across the entire care pathway from first test to post-cure monitoring, harm reduction organizations are filling the gaps left by underfunded health systems.

More Than Testing

Harm reduction organizations are doing far more than just needle exchange. In 38 cities, they provide information about Hepatitis C testing and treatment. In 34 cities, staff physically accompany clients to medical appointments. In 32 cities, they help people with the paperwork required to access healthcare.

This is advocacy work, case management, social work, and patient navigation, delivered by organizations that largely operate without stable public funding. In 29 cities, harm reduction staff can refer people who test positive directly to treatment providers.

How Harm Reduction Services Support the HCV Care Journey?

Figure 9. How do harm reduction services in your city support the following non-medical aspects of HCV care? (n=42).

Limitations Faced by Harm Reduction Organizations

Figure 10. Which (if any) of the following factors creates serious limitations for harm reduction organizations to address HCV better in your city? (n=42).

Chronically Underfunded

61.9% (26 out of 42) of cities report that harm reduction organizations face serious limitations in delivering care.

The most common constraints: insufficient or unpredictable funding (21 cities) and not enough staff (16 cities). These organizations are performing essential public health functions and being expected to do it without the resources to do it well.

After Cure: The Re-Testing Gap

Hepatitis C re-infection after successful treatment is a real risk for people who continue to inject drugs. Systematic re-testing after treatment is essential to catch re-infection early and offer treatment again. Yet our data reveals a critical gap in post-cure follow-up.

Key Figures

- **21** cities have systematic re-testing in place for people who remain at risk after curing.
- **10** cities only re-test sometimes, depending on circumstances, leaving outcomes to chance.
- **7** cities report no systematic re-testing at all, a major gap in eliminating the virus.
- **4** cities did not provide data on this indicator.
- **79%** of cities do not use drug use as a barrier to offering re-treatment after re-infection.

Re-Treatment More Accessible

In 33 of 42 cities, drug use is not used as a criterion when deciding whether to offer re-treatment to someone who becomes re-infected. This is positive compared to the treatment access barriers described above and shows that in some places, attitudes toward treatment of people who use drugs are positive.

📍 Frontline Voice [Antwerp]

"We offer re-testing every year, but we can only fund four RNA tests per person."

GIG Free Clinic in Antwerp runs a re-testing program for clients who have been cured of Hepatitis C and remain at risk. But limitations of national reimbursement create a structural constraint on follow-up care.

5

Discrimination & Stigma

Stigma Kills: Discrimination Across the Healthcare System

Testing is widely available. Treatment exists. Yet people who use drugs are not reaching care at the rates HCV elimination requires. Frontline data offers an uncomfortable explanation: across European healthcare settings, people who use drugs are treated differently than other patients: less respect, less information, different medical advice, and in some cases, outright refusal.

Frontline Voice [Valletta]

"Although it is very difficult to know what level of discrimination is still present, when looking at the lack of basic services, and practically no representation in decision making and/or discussion of drug policy one may observe that discrimination is being played out in a very subtle way. Therefore, although we are far away from people being left in the sun to do chores for hours for not obeying an order [this was a common practice in a rehabilitation center], levels of discrimination continue to negatively impact the right to health for people who use drugs."

Figure 11. Does stigma and discrimination towards people who use drugs happen at the following points of HCV care (testing and treatment) in your city? (n=42).

Figure 12. Combined reports of discrimination against people who use drugs, by healthcare setting (sum across discrimination types, n = 42 cities, 2025).

Discrimination is Widespread

Focal Points in our network reported on discrimination against people who use drugs across four key healthcare settings. The findings are alarming. At General Practitioners, 26 of 42 cities report that people who use drugs are treated with significantly less empathy or respect. At Pharmacies, 25 of 42 cities report the same. These are the first points of contact with the healthcare system, and they are already excluding people before they even reach a Hepatitis C specialist.

At Gastroenterology and Infectious Disease Clinics, the settings where Hepatitis C treatment is most commonly provided, 9 of 42 cities report that providers avoid or refuse treatment to people known to use drugs.

Frontline Voice [Lisbon]

"Discrimination accessing services: health, social, legal. It can get worse once people who use drugs are also migrants, women or LGBTIQ+."

The Discrimination Cascade

Discrimination is not a single event; focal points consistently describe this as a cascade. A person who is treated with contempt at a general practitioner's office is less likely to seek care again. A person who is refused treatment at a specialist clinic may give up entirely. The cumulative effect of everyday discrimination is that people who need care most are the least likely to receive it.

What Discrimination Looks Like in Practice

- Providers giving different medical advice or different levels of pain management based on drug use history.
- Deliberately slow appointment times or service delays for people known to use drugs
- Requiring drug tests or additional documentation before Hepatitis C treatment is offered.
- Outright refusal to treat patients who are currently using drugs.
- Hostile or disrespectful language in clinical encounters.

Extra Documentation Required

At Gastroenterology and Infectious Disease Clinics, the primary venues for Hepatitis C treatment, some cities report that additional requirements (more documentation, drug tests) are imposed on people who use drugs, requirements not asked of other patients.

What Harm Reduction Services Do Instead

- Meet people where they are, without judgment about current drug use.
- Provide accurate Hepatitis C information in accessible language.
- Help navigate complex healthcare bureaucracy.
- Accompany clients to appointments to reduce the risk of discrimination affecting care.
- Advocate with clinicians on behalf of their clients.

6

**Comparisons
across 2020-
2025**

Comparisons of development in 23 cities 2020-2025

Respondents from 23 Focal Points contributed to every annual round from 2020 to 2025. For survey items that remained unchanged across this period, we compared answers year-on-year to track development. This sub-sample skews toward Western and Northern Europe, so trends here should not be read as representative of the wider 42-city cohort.

These 23 FPs include: Amsterdam (Netherlands), Antwerp (Belgium), Athens-Thessaloniki (Greece), Barcelona (Spain), Berlin (Germany), Bern (Switzerland), Bratislava (Slovakia), Budapest (Hungary), Copenhagen (Denmark), Krakow (Poland), Dublin (Ireland), Glasgow (Scotland), Helsinki (Finland), Ljubljana (Slovenia), London (England, UK), Milan (Italy), Nicosia (Cyprus), Paris (France), Porto (Portugal), Prague (Czechia), Tallinn (Estonia), Tirana (Albania), and Vienna (Austria).

Confirmatory Hepatitis C Virus testing in prisons trends upward, reaching 16 of 23 cities in 2025, the highest point in the series. Infectious Disease Clinics remain the most common setting but have slipped from a 2020 peak of 22 to 19 in 2025. Pharmacies hold 1-2 cities every year, the least common setting.

Figure 13. Cities providing confirmatory HCV testing for people who use drugs, by setting, 2020–2025 (n = 23 longitudinal Focal Points). Harm reduction / community centers not asked in 2024.

Direct Anti-Viral Treatment Locations

DAA treatment in prisons jumped to 20 of 23 cities in 2025, the series peak, and now nearly level with Gastroenterology

and Infectious Disease Clinics. The following cities report having treatment available at prisons since 2025: Athens-Thessaloniki, Barcelona, Bern, Budapest, Copenhagen, Krakow, Nicosia, and Tirana.

General Practitioners dropped to their lowest point (3 of 23). Treatment access appears to be consistently low at primary health care settings.

Figure 14. Cities providing DAA treatment for people who inject drugs, by setting, 2020–2025 (n = 23 longitudinal Focal Points). Same caveats as Figure 14: harm reduction / community centers absent from the 2024 round.

7

Call to Action

Call to Action: Six Actions to Close the Gap

These are the most urgent priorities identified from our frontline civil society monitoring.

1. Ensure Sustainable Funding and Strengthen the Hepatitis C Care Continuum

Harm reduction services are delivering essential public health interventions on the frontline, yet they continue to operate without stable, structural funding. Governments must commit to multi-year, predictable financing for organizations providing testing, referral, and care navigation. At the same time, formal partnerships between healthcare providers, including gastroenterologists and hepatologists, must be strengthened to ensure a fully functioning hepatitis C care cascade.

2. End Discriminatory Barriers to Testing and Treatment

Denying hepatitis C treatment on the basis of current drug use is not clinically justified, it is discrimination. This practice directly undermines elimination goals and violates the principle of equitable healthcare. National guidelines and clinical practices must explicitly prohibit such exclusion and ensure that all individuals are offered timely testing and treatment, regardless of drug use status.

3. Ensure Universal Access Regardless of Legal or Insurance Status

Hepatitis C does not recognise borders, legal categories, or insurance coverage. Excluding migrants, refugees, and uninsured individuals from testing and treatment is both unjust and a direct threat to public health. Universal, free, and low-threshold access to hepatitis C services must be guaranteed for everyone.

4. Decentralize Care: Deliver Services Where People Are

Testing, treatment, and follow-up care must be brought into community-based and low-threshold settings. These services already have the trust and reach needed to engage populations most affected by hepatitis C, yet they are too often restricted from delivering care. Regulatory and structural barriers must be removed to enable community providers to deliver the full continuum of services.

5. Confront Stigma and Institutional Discrimination

Stigma and discrimination within healthcare settings remain widespread across Europe, particularly toward people who use drugs. Mandatory training, enforceable accountability mechanisms, and the meaningful involvement of affected communities in service design and delivery are essential to ensure equitable care.

6. Prioritize Re-Testing and Continuity of Care

Curing hepatitis C is not the end of risk. Reinfection remains a reality, particularly for people who continue to inject drugs. Without systematic re-testing, elimination efforts will fail. Governments must implement routine re-testing protocols and ensure continuity of care to sustain long-term public health outcomes.

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